

Developing Tourist Retention Behavior Through Tourist Experiences and Service Quality

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the influence of tourist experiences and service quality on tourist retention behavior, with tourist satisfaction acting as a mediating variable, in the context of artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan, Indonesia. Employing a quantitative causal research design, data were collected from 156 tourists through structured questionnaires and analyzed using SmartPLS. The findings reveal that both tourist experiences and service quality significantly impact tourist satisfaction and, in turn, positively affect tourist retention behavior. The key dimensions of tourist experience are local culture, psychological refreshment, and knowledge along with the five SERVQUAL dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy play crucial roles in shaping tourists' perceptions and loyalty. The study highlights that service quality has the strongest direct influence on tourist satisfaction and subsequent retention behavior. These insights offer both theoretical contributions to consumer behavior and tourism loyalty literature and practical implications for destination managers. By enhancing service standards and curating meaningful experiences, tourism stakeholders can improve visitor satisfaction, stimulate return visits, and foster long-term sustainable tourism.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourist retention behavior is the tendency of tourists to return to a tourist destination in the future based on positive experiences during previous visits. This behavior is highly dependent on the level of tourist satisfaction and emotional attachment to the destination. Tourist retention is important in sustainable tourism destination management, as repeat visits can increase local income and strengthen the destination's competitiveness in the global market. Chen et al. (2023) found that tourist retention behavior is closely related to satisfaction factors, where satisfied tourists are more likely to return to the destination and consider revisiting. Factors influencing tourist retention behavior are crucial in designing effective marketing strategies to increase tourist revisit rates.

Research on *tourist retention behavior* is fundamental because tourist retention behavior plays a key role in the long-term success of a tourist destination. *Tourist retention behavior* refers to the tendency of tourists to revisit the same destination and recommend it to others. Jalilvand & Samiei (2012) found that studying tourist retention behavior is important for ensuring the long-term sustainability of tourist destinations. Returning tourists contribute significantly to local income without requiring high promotional costs to

attract new tourists. Kozak (2001) suggests that destinations that can retain tourists who have already visited will be more economically stable and less dependent on promotion to attract new tourists. Reichheld & Sasser (1990) demonstrate that increasing customer retention by 5% can boost company profits by 25-95%.

Retaining tourists who have already visited a destination reduces the need to incur high costs in promotion. Reichheld & Sasser (1990) demonstrate that increasing customer retention by 5% can boost company profits by 25-95%. Retaining tourists who have visited a destination in a tourism context can reduce the need for high promotional costs. *Tourist retention behavior* also has an impact on *word-of-mouth marketing* and destination reputation. Satisfied tourists who return to a destination tend to recommend it to family, friends, or even through social media, which can influence other tourists' decisions to visit. Jalilvand & Samiei (2012) suggest that recommendations from satisfied tourists significantly influence attracting new tourists. *Tourist retention behavior* can help tourism stakeholders understand the factors influencing loyalty and satisfaction. Chen & Tsai (2007) indicate that the quality of the tourist experience and satisfaction play an important role in encouraging tourists to

revisit the same destination. *Tourist retention behavior* is important to help destinations cope with increasing global competition, as there are now more tourist destinations worldwide. Destinations that want to remain competitive must strive to retain existing tourists. Buhalis (2000) states that tourist destinations must be able to create unique and memorable experiences to encourage tourists to return to the same destination.

Based on the background of the study above, several objectives can be formulated: To describe *tourist experiences*, service quality, tourist satisfaction, and *tourist retention behavior*. To analyze the influence of *tourist experiences* and service quality on *tourist retention behavior* in tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. Based on the above, this study has several benefits, namely: This study guides tourism industry stakeholders in Central Kalimantan, including destination managers, tour operators, and tourism service providers, to improve service quality and pay attention to the overall tourist experience. Tourist satisfaction is important in encouraging repeat visits and recommending destinations to others. This study contributes theoretically by expanding research in tourism management, particularly *consumer satisfaction and loyalty theory*, and *the expectation-confirmation model (ECM)* related to *tourist retention behavior* through the approach of *tourist experiences* and service quality. This study enriches the understanding of the relationship between tourist experiences, service quality, and tourist satisfaction as mediating variables influencing tourists' decisions to return to a destination. This study refers to the *customer satisfaction and loyalty theory* developed by Oliver (1997). *Customer satisfaction and loyalty theory* states that customer satisfaction plays an important role in building long-term loyalty, which is demonstrated through *repeat purchase* behavior or retention behavior in the context of tourism. Oliver's (1997) theory of customer satisfaction and loyalty is the foundation for understanding consumer behavior and decision-making processes. Oliver (1997) argues that customer satisfaction is an emotional response resulting from comparing customer expectations and the actual performance of a product or service. If performance exceeds expectations, customers experience positive satisfaction, while the gap between performance and expectations can lead to dissatisfaction. Oliver (1997) emphasizes that satisfaction is not a one-time event but a dynamic process influenced by previous expectations, needs, and the evolving experiences of consumers.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study is categorized as causal associative research using a quantitative approach. This study will explain the influencing and influenced relationships of each variable studied: the influence of *tourist experiences* and service quality on *tourist retention behavior*.

B. Research Population and Sample

The population in this study consists of tourists who have visited at least once in a tourist destination in Central Kalimantan during December 2024. The sample determination technique used in this study is the Slovin formula. The sample size is 156.19, rounded to 156 people. The sampling technique used is *proportional random sampling*.

C. Data Collection Techniques

Data was collected using a survey method, which involved submitting written statements in questionnaires to respondents. These tourists had visited at least one tourist attraction in Central Kalimantan. In this study, data collection was conducted through primary data collection using questionnaires, which involved providing a list of written statements to respondents to be answered, either directly or with research guidance if necessary.

D. Data Analysis Techniques

Descriptive analysis will describe the questionnaire data using SPSS (*Statistical Package for the Social Sciences*) for Windows 21. The collected data will then be edited, coded, and tabulated for easier understanding. The interpretation of the descriptive analysis will be presented in the form of frequency distribution tables.

III. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 RESEARCH FINDINGS

This perceptual study explains how respondents view *tourist experiences*, service quality, and *tourist retention behavior*. The study's results are explained in sequence according to the study's objectives. The respondents in this study were tourists who had visited at least once tourist attractions in Central Kalimantan, totaling 156 respondents. The table below presents the characteristics of the study respondents, including gender, number of visits, and age.

Table 1. Characteristics of Research Respondents

Demographics	Frequency
Gender	
Male	58 (37)
Female	98 (63%)
Number of Visits	
1 time	68 (44%)
2 times	31
>3 times	57 (36%)
Age	
<20 years	23 (15%)
21–30 years	80 (51%)
>31 years	53 (34%)

Source: Appendix

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The table above illustrates the demographic characteristics of the respondents in this study. Based on gender, most respondents were female, totaling 98 people (63%), while male respondents numbered 58 people (37%). In terms of the frequency of visits to tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan, 68 respondents (44%) had visited the tourist location once, 31 respondents (20%) had visited twice, and 57 respondents (36%) had visited more than three times. Meanwhile, the distribution based on age shows that respondents under the age of 20 numbered 23 (15%), those aged 21–30 dominated with 80 (51%), and respondents aged over 31 numbered 53 (34%). This data indicates that most respondents are young women within the productive age

range who are actively visiting artificial tourist destinations, both as first-time and repeat visitors. Results of Descriptive Analysis, The respondents' perceptions of the research subject can be seen in the descriptive analysis results. The variables studied include *tourist experiences*, service quality, and *tourist retention behavior*.

Description of the *Tourist Experiences* Variable (X_1)

This variable consists of three indicators: *local culture* ($X_{1.1}$), *refreshing* ($X_{1.2}$), and *knowledge* ($X_{1.3}$). Respondents' responses to the *tourist experiences* indicators are shown in the table below:

Table 2. Description of Questionnaire Response Data
Tourist Experiences (X_1)

Item	Respondent Responses										Mean
	1		2		3		4		5		
	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	
X_{111}	0	0	0	0	13	8	44	28	99	64	4.55
X_{112}	0	0	0	0	13	8	28	18	115	74	4.65
<i>Local Culture</i> ($X_{1.1}$)											4.6
X_{121}	0	0	0	0	15	10	28	18	113	72	4.63
X_{122}	0	0	0	0	20	13	37	24	99	63	4.51
<i>Refreshing</i> ($X_{1.2}$)											4.57
X_{131}	0	0	0	0	8	5	42	27	106	68	4.63
X_{132}	0	0	0	0	10	6	37	24	109	70	4.63
<i>Knowledge</i> ($X_{1.3}$)											4.63
Average Tourist Experience Variable (X_1)											4.6

Source: Appendix

Table Notes:

- $X_{1.1.1}$ = Local cultural traditions
- $X_{1.1.2}$ = Respecting customary rules
- $X_{1.2.1}$ = Helping to relieve stress
- $X_{1.2.2}$ = Providing a refreshing effect
- $X_{1.3.1}$ = Enriches knowledge
- $X_{1.3.2}$ = Gaining new knowledge

Based on the table above regarding the frequency distribution of respondents' answers about *tourist experiences*, the level of *tourist experiences* of respondents regarding tourist attractions in general is relatively high. The overall average score for *the tourist experiences* variable is 4.60, which indicates that respondents strongly agree with *the tourist experiences* at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. *Tourist experiences* were analyzed through three leading indicators: *local culture*, *refreshing*, and *knowledge*. In the *local culture* indicator, the average score was 4.60. Respondents agreed that local cultural traditions are still preserved, with a mean of 4.55, and that the community respects rules for environmental preservation, with a mean of

4.65. Most respondents strongly agreed with these statements, indicating they can represent *local culture* at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan.

The *refreshing* indicator, which reflects the refreshing effect of the experience, has an average value of 4.57. The statement "helps relieve stress" obtained a mean of 4.63, while "provides a refreshing effect" obtained a mean of 4.51. This shows that respondents strongly agree and consider it representative of *the refreshing* aspect of artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. The *knowledge* indicator, which reflects tourists' knowledge in traveling, has an average score of 4.63. The statement "enriching knowledge" obtained a mean of 4.63, and "gaining new knowledge" obtained a mean of 4.63. This shows that respondents gained new knowledge during their trip. Respondents to this statement strongly agreed and were considered to represent *knowledge* at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. Overall, the average score for the *tourist experiences* variable (X_1) was 4.60, indicating that respondents' perceptions of their overall tourism experience were perfect. This result reinforces that the tourism experience factor is one of the important aspects that tourists perceive positively at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan.

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Description of the Service Quality Variable (X_2). This variable consists of five indicators, namely *tangibles* ($X_{2.1}$), *reliability* ($X_{2.2}$), *responsiveness* ($X_{2.3}$), *assurance*

($X_{2.4}$), and *empathy* ($X_{2.5}$). Respondents' responses to service quality can be seen in the table below:

Table 3. Description of Questionnaire Response Data Service Quality (X_2)

Item	Respondent Responses										Mean
	1		2		3		4		5		
	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	
X_{211}	0	0	0	0	14	9	45	29	97	62	4.53
X_{212}	0	0	0	0	14	9	51	33	91	58	4.49
<i>Tangibles</i> (X_{21})											4.51
X_{221}	0	0	0	0	17	11	48	31	91	58	4.47
X_{222}	0	0	0	0	14	9	56	36	86	55	4.46
<i>Reliability</i> (X_{22})											4.46
X_{231}	0	0	0	0	18	11	45	29	93	60	4.48
X_{232}	0	0	0	0	19	12	49	31	88	57	4.44
<i>Responsiveness</i> (X_{23})											4.46
X_{241}	0	0	0	0	10	6	49	31	97	63	4.56
X_{242}	0	0	0	0	12	8	42	27	102	65	4.58
<i>Assurance</i> (X_{24})											4.57
X_{251}	0	0	0	0	13	8	45	29	98	63	4.54
X_{252}	0	0	0	0	16	10	42	27	98	63	4.53
<i>Empathy</i> (X_{25})											4.53
Average Service Quality Variable (X_2)											4.5

Source: Appendix

Table Notes:

- $X_{2.1.1}$ = Clean facilities
- $X_{2.1.2}$ = Availability of facilities
- $X_{2.2.1}$ = Tourist services
- $X_{2.2.2}$ = Consistency of information
- $X_{2.3.1}$ = Quick response
- $X_{2.3.2}$ = Ability to provide solutions
- $X_{2.4.1}$ = Safe service
- $X_{2.4.2}$ = Safety assurance
- $X_{2.5.1}$ = Attention to tourist comfort
- $X_{2.5.2}$ = Emotional needs

Based on the table above regarding the frequency distribution of respondents' answers about the service quality variable, most respondents gave positive assessments of the service quality provided by artificial tourist destinations. The overall average score for the service quality variable is 4.50, indicating that respondents strongly agree with the quality of service at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. Service quality was analyzed through five leading indicators: *tangibles*, *reliability*, *responsiveness*, *assurance*, and *empathy*. *Tangible* indicators obtained an average score of 4.53, indicating that the physical facilities of the destination were considered adequate and well-maintained. Respondents rated cleanliness with a mean of 4.53 and availability of facilities with a mean of 4.49. Most respondents agreed with these statements, which were considered representative of the *tangible aspects* of tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan.

The *reliability* indicator, which reflects tourists' trust in consistent and reliable services, had an average score of 4.46. The statement on tourism services received a mean of 4.47, while the consistency of information received a mean of 4.46. This indicates that respondents agreed and considered these indicators to represent *reliability* at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. The *responsiveness* indicator indicates that tourists feel they are served quickly and responsively, with an average score of 4.46. The statement "quickly responds to tourist requests" obtained a mean of 4.48, and "able to provide solutions" obtained a mean of 4.44. Respondents to this statement agreed and were considered to represent *responsiveness* at tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan.

The *assurance* indicator, which shows that aspects of safety and confidence in services are the main strengths of the destination, has a mean of 4.57. The statement regarding safe services during the trip obtained a mean of 4.56, and safety guarantees obtained a mean of 4.58. Respondents to this statement strongly agree and are considered to represent *assurance* at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. The *empathy* indicator shows that the managers of the artificial tourist destination pay considerable attention to personalization and empathy towards visitors, with a mean score of 4.53. Service statements demonstrating attention to comfort have a mean score of 4.54, and statements regarding staff understanding of visitors' feelings have a mean score of 4.53. Respondents to these statements expressed strong

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agreement and considered them to represent *empathy* at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. The mean for the service quality variable (X_2) was 4.50, indicating that respondents' perceptions of service quality were perfect. This finding reinforces the important role of service quality in shaping positive tourist experiences at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan.

Description of the *Tourist Retention Behavior* (Y) Variable
The *tourist retention behavior* variable consists of four indicators, namely return visits ($Y_{2.1}$), *word of mouth* ($Y_{2.2}$), recommendations ($Y_{2.3}$), and trust ($Y_{2.4}$). The results of the descriptive analysis are explained in the table below:

Table 4. Description of Data Results of the Questionnaire Tourist Retention Behavior (Y_2)

Item	Respondent's Response										Mean
	1		2		3		4		5		
	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	Σ	%	
Y_{211}	0	0	0	0	14	9	42	27	100	64	4.55
Y_{212}	0	0	0	0	14	9	46	30	96	61	4.53
Return visits (Y_{21})											4.54
Y_{221}	0	0	0	0	13	8	50	32	93	60	4.51
Y_{222}	0	0	0	0	14	9	48	31	94	60	4.51
Word of Mouth (Y_{21})											4.51
Y_{231}	0	0	0	0	15	10	46	30	95	60	4.51
Y_{232}	0	0	0	0	12	8	43	28	101	64	4.57
Recommend (Y_{21})											4.54
Y_{241}	0	0	0	0	14	9	52	33	90	58	4.49
Y_{242}	0	0	0	0	16	10	43	28	97	62	4.52
Confidence (Y_{21})											4.5
Average Tourist Retention Behavior Variable (Y_2)											4.5

Source: Appendix

Table Notes:

- $Y_{2.1.1}$ = Intend to visit again.
- $Y_{2.1.2}$ = Satisfaction with revisit
- $Y_{2.2.1}$ = Direct experience stories
- $Y_{2.2.2}$ = Social media experience stories
- $Y_{2.3.1}$ = Recommend to others
- $Y_{2.3.2}$ = Recommending to family
- $Y_{2.4.1}$ = Trust in comfort
- $Y_{2.4.2}$ = Facilities meet expectations

Based on the table above regarding the frequency distribution of respondents' answers about *tourist retention behavior*, which reflects the tendency of tourists to return, recommend destinations, and build trust in the tourist attractions they visit. The overall average of the *tourist retention behavior* variable is 4.52, indicating that respondents strongly agree with *tourist retention behavior* at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. *Tourist retention behavior* was analyzed through four primary indicators: revisiting, *word of mouth*, recommending, and trust. The indicators of intention to return and satisfaction with the visit, which have means of 4.55 and 4.53, respectively, show that respondents strongly agree and are considered representative of return visits. This indicates that tourists have the intention and satisfaction to return to tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. *Word of mouth* indicators, which include statements about sharing experiences directly and through social media, had a mean of

4.54 and 4.51. Respondents generally showed a willingness to share their experiences with others, both face-to-face and online, reflecting informal positive promotion by visitors. Respondents to this statement strongly agreed and were considered representative of *word of mouth* at tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan.

The indicator recommendations include recommendations to others and family, each with a mean of 4.51 and 4.56. This reflects a strong desire to recommend visits to those closest to them. Respondents to this statement strongly agreed and were considered representative of those who would recommend artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. Trust indicators, which include statements of trust in comfort and fulfillment of expectations, had a mean value of 4.49 and 4.50. This indicates that tourists are satisfied with the services and facilities available and feel that the destination meets their expectations. Respondents to this statement agreed and were considered to represent trust in artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. Overall, the mean value of the *tourist retention behavior* variable (Y_2) was 4.52, which is classified as very good. This indicates that most respondents positively perceived the tourist destinations they visited and showed a high tendency to return, recommend, and build trust in these destinations. These findings reinforce the importance of positive experiences in shaping tourist loyalty to artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. The model fit generated from Smart-PLS shows an acceptable fit. The table below

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shows that tourist satisfaction (Y_1) is influenced by *tourist experiences* (X_1) and service quality (X_2). *Tourist retention behavior* (Y_2) is influenced by *tourist experiences* (X_1), service quality (X_2), and tourist satisfaction (Y_1). The

following table shows the direct effects on each relationship between variables.

Table 5. Testing Direct and Indirect Influence Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Path	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	P Values	Description
Hypothesis	$X_1 \rightarrow Y_2$	0.420	0.084	0	Significant
	$X_2 \rightarrow Y_2$	0.558	0.078	0	Significant

Source: Appendix

The following is an explanation of the results of the hypothesis testing based on the table above, including:

3.2 DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the above research, the discussion of the research results can be compiled based on the research objectives as follows: *Tourist experiences* are defined as the overall subjective perceptions formed through the direct involvement of tourists in tourism activities, encompassing emotional, cognitive, and sensory aspects. In the context of artificial tourism in Central Kalimantan, rich in local culture, ecotourism, and biodiversity, these *experiences* can be explained through three indicators: *local culture*, *refreshing*, and *knowledge*. *Local culture* experiences include tourists' involvement with community traditions, participation in traditional ceremonies, watching local performances, and tasting traditional cuisine. These activities provide authentic value, enriching tourists' interactions with the destination and enhancing meaningful experiences (Richards, 2011). The *refreshing* aspect focuses on feelings of relaxation, mental renewal, and relief from the stress of daily routines. Artificial tourism in Central Kalimantan offers peaceful nature tourism such as river tours, tropical rainforests, and encounters with orangutans, all serving as calming recreational activities (Tung & Ritchie, 2011). The knowledge dimension encompasses learning when tourists gain new insights into nature, culture, and local history. Activities like visits to orangutan conservation centers, cultural museums, and interactions with local guides provide significant educational value (Falk et al., 2012).

The tourist experience in Central Kalimantan is shaped by a blend of authentic local culture, refreshing natural beauty, and opportunities to gain new knowledge. These three indicators complement each other and play an important role in creating a memorable and valuable tourist experience. The development of artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan needs to integrate these three aspects in a balanced manner to increase tourist attraction and satisfaction sustainably. Service quality in the tourism sector is tourists' perception regarding the extent to which the

services provided by destination managers meet or exceed expectations. Service quality in the context of artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan greatly determines the experience of tourists and the region's image, contributing to satisfaction and repeat visits. Physical evidence includes facilities available at tourist destinations, such as infrastructure, cleanliness, information equipment, signage, and comfort. The presence of tourist piers, cultural information boards, and well-maintained accommodation facilities reflects the professionalism and readiness of managers (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

Reliability indicates the ability of tourism managers to deliver promised services accurately and consistently, such as tour schedules, guide services, or transportation. Reliability can be seen from the punctuality of river tours or the accuracy of transportation of tourists to conservation sites (Zeithaml et al., 1996). *Responsiveness* is the willingness and speed of service providers to assist tourists and provide fast services. This includes the ability of staff to handle tourist requests, answer questions, and respond to complaints promptly (Grönroos, 2007). *Assurance* relates to the knowledge and friendliness of staff, as well as their ability to make tourists feel safe. Tour guides in Central Kalimantan who understand local flora and fauna and are trained in safety procedures provide confidence and comfort to visitors (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Empathy reflects the personal attention and friendly attitude of staff toward tourists. Artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan demonstrate empathy through the friendliness of the local community, their willingness to listen to tourists' complaints, and the provision of special services for vulnerable groups such as the elderly or children (Ladhari, 2009). The synergy between adequate physical evidence, service reliability, staff responsiveness, safety guarantees, and empathy toward tourists shapes the quality of service at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. The consistent application of the five dimensions of SERVQUAL can enhance tourist satisfaction and loyalty, while also strengthening the destination's long-term competitiveness. Tourist satisfaction is a positive psychological condition that arises from evaluating a tourist's experience after visiting a destination, reflecting the match between initial expectations

and perceived reality. Tourist attractions include the uniqueness and beauty of nature, culture, and activities a destination offers. Central Kalimantan has attractive features such as Tanjung Puting National Park, Dayak culture, betang houses, and river tours. These attractions form a strong first impression of the destination (Chen & Tsai, 2007). Transportation access, accommodation, restaurants, information centers, and public toilets greatly influence tourist comfort. Ease of access to tourist sites and the availability of basic facilities are determinants of visitor satisfaction (Baker & Crompton, 2000).

Safety encompasses a sense of security from physical threats, accident risks, and safety guarantees during tourist activities. Safety is crucial in areas with natural activities such as forests and rivers, as is common in Central Kalimantan (Reisinger & Mavondo, 2005). Emotional experiences encompass feelings of happiness, awe, or being moved that tourists feel while at a destination. This factor creates a deep impression that can increase memory retention and the intention to revisit (Tung & Ritchie, 2011). Tourist satisfaction at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan is formed by destination attractiveness, adequate facilities, guaranteed safety, and touching emotional experiences. These four indicators complement each other in creating a comprehensive and memorable tourism experience. To maintain and improve tourist satisfaction, destination managers must manage local uniqueness professionally and sustainably.

Tourist retention behavior refers to the tendency of tourists to remain loyal to a destination, whether in the form of repeat visits, voluntary promotion, or the formation of long-term relationships. Retention behavior is significant for sustainable tourism development, especially given the characteristics of destinations that rely on the uniqueness of Dayak culture and natural beauty. The tendency of tourists to revisit a destination indicates high levels of satisfaction and interest. In Central Kalimantan, the desire to return can be influenced by positive experiences with the wild (such as Tanjung Puting National Park), the friendliness of residents, or memorable cultural experiences (Chi & Qu, 2008). *Word-of-mouth* is the act of travelers sharing positive experiences with others, either verbally or through social media. Organic WOM is very important in expanding the reputation of tourist destinations that are not yet very popular, such as Central Kalimantan (Litvin, Goldsmith, & Pan, 2008). A concrete form of WOM is the willingness of travelers to recommend destinations to family, friends, or social networks. These recommendations are influenced by tourists' overall experience during their visit (Yoon & Uysal, 2005).

Trust in a destination includes believing the place is safe, comfortable, and consistently provides positive experiences. In Central Kalimantan, trust can arise from professional service, safety of tourist activities, and authenticity of local culture (Casaló, Flavián, & Guinalú, 2010). Tourist retention behavior in Central Kalimantan is

influenced by the desire to return, voluntarily share experiences, recommend the destination to others, and trust in the destination. Strengthening these dimensions is crucial for tourism managers in maintaining visitor loyalty and creating sustainable tourism based on culture and nature. Destination development strategies that emphasize quality of experience, safety, and emotional value will increase the likelihood of tourist retention in the long term. As a leading artificial tourist destination, Central Kalimantan boasts a rich Dayak culture, ecotourism sites such as Tanjung Puting National Park, and unique wilderness experiences. *Tourist experiences* play a crucial role in shaping *tourist retention behavior*, which refers to the tendency of tourists to return, provide recommendations, share positive information, and build long-term trust in a destination. *Tourist experiences* encompass *local culture, refreshment, and knowledge*, providing tourists with holistic and emotional experiences. When tourists feel emotionally connected, gain new insights, and enjoy authentic local culture, this creates memorable and meaningful experiences that will generate the intention to return, recommend the destination to others, and strengthen trust in the destination, all of which are components of *tourist retention behavior*. Several studies support the positive influence of tourist experiences on loyalty or retention behavior. Tung & Ritchie (2011) state that emotional and memorable travel experiences can predict the intention to revisit.

Chen & Tsai (2007) showed that positive perceptions of tourism experiences have a direct influence on destination loyalty, and Kim et al. (2012) explained that authentic and immersive experiences significantly influence word-of-mouth (WOM) and recommendations. In the context of artificial tourism in Central Kalimantan, the stronger the quality of the tourism experience perceived (both culturally, educationally, and emotionally), the greater the tendency for tourists to exhibit positive retention behavior. Positive tourism experiences in Central Kalimantan, shaped through interaction with local culture, emotional refreshment, and knowledge acquisition, significantly influence tourist retention behavior. Tourists who feel satisfied and impressed are more likely to have a strong desire to return, recommend the destination to others, and trust the destination's reputation in the long term.

Local tourism managers need to focus on improving the quality of the tourist experience as a strategy to retain tourists and build sustainable tourism. The success of a tourist destination is determined not only by its natural or cultural attractions but also by the quality of service provided to tourists. Service quality is key to fostering *tourist retention behavior*, such as the intention to return, recommendations, and trust in the destination. Good service quality creates satisfaction and builds trust, encouraging tourists to revisit the destination, spreading positive *word-of-mouth*, and developing loyalty toward the destination. Several studies support a direct relationship between service quality and

tourist retention. Kandampully & Suhartanto (2000) found that in the tourism industry, service quality directly impacts customer loyalty, as indicated by the intention to revisit. Ladhari (2009) emphasized that perceptions of service dimensions contribute to the formation of tourist loyalty through emotional satisfaction and trust. Raza et al. (2012) demonstrated that service quality influences *customer retention* by enhancing positive perceptions of the tourism experience. Comprehensive service quality, from tourist facilities, reliability of information, and attention to tourist needs, will increase the likelihood of tourists remaining loyal and returning to the destination and promoting it voluntarily. Service quality significantly influences tourist retention behavior in Central Kalimantan's artificial tourist destinations. Good service enhances tourists' trust, satisfaction, and positive emotions, ultimately encouraging the intention to revisit, recommend the destination to others, and foster long-term trust. Implications: Destination managers in Central Kalimantan's artificial tourist destinations must consistently improve service standards across all areas, particularly in terms of hospitality, service speed, cleanliness, and safety, to build tourist loyalty and create sustainable tourism.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of *tourist experiences*, service quality, and *tourist retention behavior*, the following conclusions can be drawn: Tourist experiences in Central Kalimantan are shaped by a blend of authentic local culture, refreshing natural beauty, and opportunities to gain new knowledge. These three indicators complement each other and play an important role in creating memorable and valuable tourist experiences. The development of artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan needs to integrate these three aspects in a balanced manner to increase tourist attraction and satisfaction sustainably. The synergy between adequate physical facilities, reliable services, staff responsiveness, safety guarantees, and empathy toward tourists shapes the quality of service at artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. The consistent application of the five dimensions of SERVQUAL can enhance tourist satisfaction and loyalty, while strengthening the destination's competitiveness in the long term. Tourist retention behavior in Central Kalimantan is influenced by the desire to revisit, voluntarily share experiences, recommend the destination to others, and trust in the destination. Strengthening these dimensions is crucial for tourism managers in maintaining visitor loyalty and fostering sustainable tourism based on culture and nature. Destination development strategies that emphasize quality of experience, safety, and emotional value will increase the likelihood of tourist retention in the long term.

Positive tourism experiences in Central Kalimantan, shaped through interaction with local culture, emotional refreshment, and knowledge acquisition, significantly

influence tourist retention behavior. Tourists who feel satisfied and impressed are more likely to have a strong desire to return, recommend the destination to others, and trust the destination's reputation in the long term. Local tourism managers need to focus on improving the quality of the tourist experience as a strategy to retain tourists and build sustainable tourism.

Service quality significantly influences tourist retention behavior in artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan. Good service increases tourist trust, satisfaction, and positive emotions, ultimately encouraging repeat visits, recommendations to others, and long-term trust in the destination. Managers of artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan must consistently improve service standards across all areas, particularly in terms of hospitality, service speed, cleanliness, and safety, to build tourist loyalty and create sustainable tourism. Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that service quality variables have the most substantial direct influence on tourist satisfaction and contribute significantly to tourist retention behavior through satisfaction mediation. Managers of artificial tourist destinations in Central Kalimantan are advised to prioritize improving service quality, particularly regarding *reliability*, *responsiveness*, safety, and empathy towards visitors. *Tourist experiences* have direct and indirect significant influences on retention behavior, with relatively lower coefficient values than service quality.

The following are this research's theoretical and practical contributions: This study provides theoretical contributions by integrating *tourist experiences*, service quality, and tourist satisfaction in shaping *tourist retention behavior*. This model expands the understanding of how tourism experiences and quality services influence momentary satisfaction and encourage tourist retention behaviors such as repeat visits and positive *word-of-mouth*. This research provides practical guidance for managers of artificial tourist destinations to focus on improving tourist experiences that touch on aspects of local culture, psychological refreshment, and education, as well as enhancing service quality dimensions such as reliability, care, and safety assurance. This has been proven to influence tourist satisfaction and retention significantly. The research findings can be used as a basis for developing customer satisfaction-based management strategies, including tourism human resource training, facility improvements, and service innovations that respond to the needs of modern tourists.

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